

THE DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE COMPETENCY OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article emphasizes the importance of proper organization in inclusive education, highlighting the teacher's role in creating conducive conditions for the full development of each student. The teacher's responsibilities include identifying students needing special support, creating a comfortable classroom environment, fostering emotional well-being, mastering modern teaching methods, adapting materials, and collaborating with parents. Inclusive competence, rooted in an inclusive mindset, is crucial for teachers*

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Proper organization of educational methods in inclusive education is a factor of quality and efficiency. In inclusive education, the goal of the teacher should be to create the necessary conditions for the full realization of the potential abilities and opportunities of each child studying in an inclusive class. To achieve this goal, the teacher must perform a number of tasks. They are as follows [1]:

1. Determining the category of students who need to create special educational conditions in the classroom.
2. Creating a comfortable environment in the classroom based on the needs of the students (in inclusive classes, children with impaired hearing, impaired vision, and problems with the basic movement system can study). For example, it is necessary to leave space for the movement of a wheelchair, provide special equipment (lifting device, ramp, handrail, etc.), provide good lighting in the classroom, and equip it with magnifying devices;
3. Ability to create an emotionally comfortable environment based on cooperation and tolerance in the children's team;
4. Mastering modern methods, methods, and forms of education and being able to apply them to children with special educational needs;
5. ability to adapt educational and didactic materials or create new ones (to create tasks of different difficulty levels, to prepare workbooks, posters or presentations in large font allowing to illustrate the topic)
6. Applying acceptable methods of evaluating students' curricular and extracurricular activities based on their individual capabilities;
7. Ability to cooperate with parents and feel responsible for them.

The performance of the above tasks requires teachers teaching in inclusive classes to have a number of professional competencies. In inclusive education, the teacher's professional skills are the main factor. First of all, the teacher must have an inclusive mindset and take responsibility for the quality of education. We can collectively call these competencies inclusive competence or inclusive competence.

Inductive competence is first of all manifested in changing the teacher's professional values and individual style of activity.

The emotional state of students studying in an inclusive class directly depends on the moral and value concepts of the teacher. Children with disabilities can start their career as a teacher in an existing classroom in two ways. The first method is the traditional, stereotyping method, in which the teacher considers children with disabilities to be an "obstacle" to the education of other children. The second way is to accept changes. If the teacher chooses the second method, he should reconsider not only his professional but also his personal principles and values.

Inclusive competence of future elementary school teachers is formed first of all through a correct understanding of the category of disability. Disability is primarily an issue of human diversity and human rights. We believe that every member of society should fully understand disability, not just a medical or charity model, but a human rights model, and remove the barriers to disabled people in their minds. It is known that the number of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan officially exceeds 700 thousand. In the report published by the World Bank at the beginning of 2022, it was noted that the number of persons with disabilities in the country is 2.1% of the population. However, the numbers are actually much higher.

In Uzbekistan, the Law "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" entered into force on January 16, 2021. The main problem of our society lies in our stereotypes about "disability". This concept is still equated with a defect. This is a very medical concept. Disability is not an anomaly or just a medical issue. The Convention states that disability is not only a disability, but a concept that arises from the interaction of environment and attitudes. That is, the emergence of this situation depends not only on that person, but also on society. We can see it in the following drawings (1; 2. Figures):

1 Fig: Manifestation of disability

The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities states that "disability is a condition resulting from the interaction between people with impaired bodily functions and attitudinal and infrastructural barriers."

Disability according to the UN CRPD (Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities):

– Interactions between persons with disabilities arise as a result of attitudes and environmental barriers that prevent their full and effective participation in community life on an equal basis with others.

- Persons with disabilities include those with long-term physical, mental, intellectual, or emotional disabilities whose various limitations may prevent them from participating equally with others in society, fully and effectively.

2 Fig: Models of disability

The "social model" reinforces the social approach to disability. According to him, a person acquires disability not because of a health disorder, but because of the accidents he encounters. The "medical model" evaluates disability as a disease and inability to work. The medical concept of disability prevails in the legislation of our country. For example, the Law "On Social Protection of Disabled Persons in the Republic of Uzbekistan" defines that "a person in need of social assistance and protection due to physical or mental disabilities is considered disabled" [2].

Also, another problem is explained by the widespread adoption of the charity model in relation to disability in society. That is, to understand that the problem of people with disabilities can be solved through various donations, holidays and gifts, social allowances. This model is especially visible every year on December 3 - the International Day of Persons with Disabilities. In fact, this day is not a holiday, but a day to ensure the rights of people with disabilities, to strengthen the norms of justice and equality in society, and to raise awareness of the problems of people with disabilities. In developed countries, organizations and initiative groups of persons with disabilities unite and put forward the idea that "we need rights, not charity".

A positive and professional position of ATEB towards the child will be formed by correctly forming the category of disability in the future primary school teachers.

Inclusive competence in future primary school teachers is evident in the successful solution of the following tasks (Table 3).

3-Table

Conditions for manifestation of inclusive competence in future primary school teachers

ATEB's ability to create a conducive learning environment for children:	Ability to adapt the environment to the capabilities of the ATEB child:
Lesson content/method	Knowledge and experience
Support system (recruitment of additional specialists)	Individualized Education Program (IEP)
Qualification of the teacher	Lesson materials
Raise awareness	Equipment and equipment of the room
A positive emotional atmosphere in the classroom	Co-educational system

In schools, teachers are often used to working with student leaders. They follow the teacher quickly, understand and can show good results. A child with a disability who goes to the same school as healthy children is less likely to become a leader, because they have to spend more effort than others to hear, see and understand. It is necessary for teachers to be able to accept these things correctly and establish a good relationship with them. For this, they must first be ready. If such children enter the class of a teacher who has not taught a child with disabilities at all, he may not understand the child's language at first, and may not be able to accept his difficult learning. Therefore, teachers should be trained to work with children with disabilities

The analysis of the literature showed [3,4] that teachers with qualities such as flexibility of personal and professional qualities, resilience, willingness to solve problems, and a positive attitude towards themselves and the results of their work achieve more results in inclusive classes. One of the main criteria of inclusive competence of future elementary school teachers is that the teacher must protect and respect the rights of all children, despite the fact that the students are of different categories.

Another quality is cooperation. Because cooperation and exchange of ideas is important for teachers. In order for the teacher to systematically assess his/her performance, improve his/her qualifications regularly, apply leadership and management skills, solve problems together, and establish comprehensive school cooperation in order to discipline children with special educational needs and effectively work with inter-institutional groups [5].

Starting from the 2022/2023 academic year, the number of general education schools where inclusive education has been introduced has been increased to 195 in order to gradually develop the inclusive education system and expand its scope. 504 children with disabilities were included in the inclusive education organized in these schools. Today, 248 pedagogues are assigned to students in these inclusive classes.

The above numbers are not just indicators and numbers, but also represent the level of responsibility for the fate, future, and life of the same number of children. That is, inclusive education should become a form of quality education that guarantees clear reality and educational results, not just political publicity, illusion, lofty promises.

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